

Optimizing E-commerce Content Management Systems: Strategies For Enhanced Customer Experience and Business Growth

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to provide relief to those non-coder users who want to be a part of e-commerce but have no programming knowledge and no idea how to build an e-commerce website, so they have an Online Marketplace. Traditional CMS solutions are often less dynamic and more difficult to manage for Internet business needs. In response to this gap, this paper outlines the use of CMS state-of-the-art technology to provide robust and scalable systems. Many smaller organizations do not. It also fails to support manpower for this purpose, as well as the cost of hiring programmers. Implementation of the proposal The solution will be simple and can be built in no time. While this research provides instrumental and comprehensive Documentation to help them develop a website, this process, as mentioned, is particularly easy It takes care of non-coders. This paper contributes to the expansion of the e-commerce market as more people participate and expand their services, which benefits both CMS users and customers.

Keywords: *MERN Stack, (composed of MongoDB, Express, React.js, and Node.js), Content Management System, E-commerce Market, Non-Coders, Online Market, Products, Shopping.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this paper is to provide relief to those non-coder users who want to be a part of e-commerce but do not have programming knowledge and have no idea how to build an e-commerce website, so they have an online marketplace. Traditional CMS solutions are often less dynamic and more difficult to manage for Internet business needs. In response to this gap, this paper outlines the use of CMS state-of-the-art technology to provide robust and scalable systems. Many smaller organizations also fail to support manpower for this

purpose, as well as the cost of hiring programmers. Implementation of the proposed solution will be simple and can be built in no time. While this research provides instrumental and comprehensive documentation to help them develop a website, and this process, as mentioned, is particularly easy, it takes care of non-coders. This paper contributes to the expansion of the e-commerce market as more people participate and expand their services, which benefits both CMS users and customers.

Content management systems (CMS) play a crucial role in managing online stores efficiently.

MERN stack technology, combining MongoDB, Express, React, and Node.js, offers a robust framework for developing e-commerce platforms.

Integrating a CMS into the MERN stack architecture can streamline content creation, product management, and user experience.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In [1], Kumar, Avnish & Ijmtst, Editor. (2022). E-commerce website using full-stack web development technologies. The tabs on this website are fully functional. The page contains several websites where you can click buttons or sections to access information, such as "Home, Category, Blog, Contact," etc. The website's "Add to Cart" and "Product Information Tabs ." Now it's its own place. Some of the tabs on the site are mobile-friendly, including our mail subscription option, voice search section, login area, Stripe payment gateway, ability to add items to cart, retrieve data from MongoDB, and render using IDS.

In [2] Bhavyaa, & Gupta, Suhani & Vaishali, Ms. (2021). This review focuses on comparing the runtimes of MERN (MongoDB, Express, React.js, and Node.js) and MEVN (V stands for Vue.js) to guide the reader through choosing among the best technologies, as well as increasing their efficiency in manufacturing.

In[3], P. M. Alamdari, N. J. Navimipour, M. Hosseinzadeh, A. A. Safaei and A. Darwesh (2020). The present article presents a comprehensive and systematic literature review (SLR) of published papers on e-commerce recommender systems. We reviewed selected papers to identify gaps and important issues in traditional RS approaches, which provide researchers with directions for future work. Therefore, we presented traditional

methods, challenges, and open issues related to traditional approaches to the research area based on the selected papers.

In[4], isky, Hanif, Nurhuda., Hendri, Irawan. (2023). The study aims to develop a web-based e-commerce system using the Woocommerce plugin to facilitate online sales as an alternative to physical stores and Instagram, expand product sales, and provide customers with a great shopping experience.

In[5], Jordi, Cabot. (2018). In his paper, Jordi Cabot explores the evolution of WordPress and its importance as a powerful content management system (CMS) that changed the way content is published and managed online He has the power to deliver to individuals and organizations by providing simple tools to create, organize, and share content on the website, which reflects the process. Cabot shows how WordPress democratized publishing, enabled anyone with Internet access to digital presence, and supported online discourse The paper may explore WordPress's features, impact, and implications for the forthcoming developments in online publishing and content management, which are of great significance.

In[6], B, V, Wakode., D, N, Chaudhari. (2013). This paper compares perhaps two popular content management frameworks, Joomla and Drupal, focusing on their features, capabilities, and suitability for different projects Such research can be valuable in identifying the strengths and weaknesses of CMS options for informed decision-making in web development and e-commerce.

In[7], Wan, Amiera, Wan, Jusoh., Nor, Irvoni, Mohd, Ishar., Muhammad, Ilham, Sjahrir., Nur, Fatihah, and Shuhada, Hussin. (2022). The study aims to examine the influence of website design, website security, and customer service on the customer experience of online shopping platforms in Malaysia.

In [8], Antonia, Stefani. (2022). The paper focuses on specific web metrics related to quality assessment of business and consumer (B2C) e-commerce systems, emphasizing the importance of measuring their quality using practical methods.

In[9], Abon, Chaudhuri., Paolo, Messina., Samrat, Kokkula., Aditya, Subramanian., Abhinandan, Krishnan., S., Gandhi., Alessandro, Magnani., Venkatesh, Kandaswamy. (2018). The paper discusses the importance of

using visual aids, especially product visualizations, in e-commerce to improve customer engagement and purchasing decisions.

In[10], Joe, Yuan, Mambu., Green, Sandag., Erienika, Lompoliu., Green, Mandias., Marchel, Tombeng. (2022). The paper focuses on training students to use WordPress as a content management system (CMS) for creating websites.

3. METHODOLOGY

The implementation method placed greater emphasis on focusing on the user, creating an interface for the online store that was easy to navigate and accessible. They offered key features, including content management, Search Engine Optimization, and page automation, combined to enhance the user experience. Additionally, multilingual support and integration of AWS services highlighted the flexibility and scalability of the platform, and extensive data was effectively managed for a wide range of users. Strong security measures and integrated payment gateways served to ensure secure and seamless transactions. Users were provided with detailed surveys and documentation to help them understand the operation of their store and use the CMS effectively. Overall, it showcases a user-friendly Ecommerce CMS, highlighting usability, security, and advanced features aimed at making creating and maintaining it online easier

The research method involved a two-pronged approach, using a case study design to develop and dynamically test an Ecommerce CMS based on MERN and a comparative analysis against the Shopify Development process, which followed a structured approach. It started with careful planning to define the project objectives and requirements. Once we have therefore, subsequently selected the MERN stack accordingly in Ecommerce CMS development, the Agile method, including sprint, iterative development, was adopted due to its flexibility. A complex integration and testing process was used to ensure that the CMS creation process involved a series of steps, including database development using MongoDB, backend development using Node.js and Express.js, and front-end development using React for the interactive interface

Figure 1: User Registration and Authentication

Figure 2: Store Creation and Customization

In Figure 1, you can see the layout of the Register, Login, Profile, Manage Store, and Create Store roles. In the Register section, users can start creating their online store. Input details such as name, email, date of birth, mobile number, password, and confirmation password will be provided. Once registered, this information will be stored in the MongoDB archive, and users will be directed to the login page. To log in, users are required to enter the credentials previously used during registration. If they are successful, users are redirected to their profile page. The Profile page contains the user’s personal information and provides options for changing profiles, accessing existing stores, and creating new ones. Clicking "Create New Store" redirects users to a page with the input fields required to create the store, including store name, location, mobile number, email, and description. Once completed, the shop is set up.

As shown in Figure 2, after completing the store creation process, users will be directed to the store dashboard, with pages awaiting options including payment gateway integration, Google Capturing analytics data, changing systems, managing resources, managing analytics, and transformation. In the Layout section, users can customize the navbar, move or change the icon, adjust flags, add new items, highlight bestsellers, and create the footer customization, allowing greater customization of the e-commerce store layout. Fields are provided to enter product information such as description, quantity, price, and category, which facilitates easy addition of products in the store. The "Review" section displays the item

4. ANALYSIS

CMS is proving to be a versatile and robust solution, especially well-suited for businesses with specific requirements. While eliminating subscription fees results in economies of scale, considering initial development costs and ongoing maintenance costs, there is a commendable need for competent professionals for effective planning, innovation, and improvement. Its extensive customization options make it an ideal choice for projects or endeavors that require a customized user experience. Essentially, this CMS stands as a handy option for those with development skills, aiming to create and maintain highly personalized and customizable websites.

- **Benefits of Using a CMS for E-Commerce in MERN Stack**

- ❖ Simplifies content management by providing a user-friendly interface for non-technical users.
- ❖ Enables real-time updates and changes to product listings, pricing, and promotions.
- ❖ Enhances SEO capabilities through content optimization and structured data implementation.

❖ Features of CMS for E-commerce in MERN Stack

- ❖ Customizable templates and themes to create a unique online store design.
- ❖ Inventory management tools for tracking stock levels, sales, and order fulfillment.
- ❖ Integration with payment gateways and shipping providers for seamless transactions.

❖ Popular CMS Options for E-commerce in MERN Stack

- ❖ Shopify: Offers a comprehensive e-commerce solution with easy setup and scalability.
- ❖ WooCommerce: A WordPress plugin that provides flexibility and customization for online stores.
- ❖ Magento: Known for its robust features and advanced functionalities for large-scale e-commerce businesses.

❖ Implementing a CMS in MERN Stack Architecture

- ❖ Utilize Express.js for backend development and API integrations with the chosen CMS.
- ❖ Integrate React components for dynamic user interfaces and interactive shopping experiences.
- ❖ Leverage MongoDB for storing product data, user information, and content management.

❖ Challenges of Using a CMS for E-commerce in MERN Stack

- ❖ Ensuring data security and compliance with regulations such as GDPR and PCI DSS.
- ❖ Managing system performance and scalability to handle high traffic and peak loads.

- ❖ Balancing customization needs with out-of-the-box features provided by the CMS.
- ❖ **Future Trends in CMS for E-commerce in MERN Stack**
- ❖ Predictions on how CMS technologies will evolve to meet the changing needs of online retailers.
- ❖ Emerging trends such as headless CMS, AI-driven personalization, and voice commerce integration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result explained the entire scenario of the application "CONTENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FOR E-COMMERCE IN MERN STACK." and how the application actually looks and compares. This application is integrated with the frontend, backend, and database. And with this, every section contains many parts, like a dashboard (for adding, editing, deleting products, order management, creating blogs, making discount coupons, and many more). Shown in the figure.

Dashboard for admin panel

HERO SECTION

GRAPH-1

The below graph (GRAPH-1) is shows that how much time is taken for each operation like loading speed of our application, time to add data in a database like user registration, time to authenticate user in login, add blog, loading time of products from database.

The screenshot displays the 'Add Product' section of an admin dashboard. On the left is a dark sidebar with a yellow header 'Pixel Perfect Solution' and a menu of options: Dashboard, Customers, Catalog, Add Product (highlighted), Product List, Brand, Brand List, Category, Category List, Color, Color List, and Orders. The main content area has a light gray background and is titled 'Add Product'. It contains four input fields: 'Enter Product Title', a rich text editor with a toolbar (Normal, Bold, Italic, Underline, Link, Unlink, Bulleted List, Numbered List, Strikethrough), 'Enter Product Price', and 'Select Brand'.

ADMIN ADD PRODUCT SECTION

Applications have many features, like analyzing product and website reaches to maintain the products. Basically, the frontend is normal, like the user can easily use it, and every route page is available to help the user experience. There is a “HOME PAGE, HERO-SECTION, ADMIN PAGE, REGISTRATION PAGE, CONTACT PAGE, USER LOGIN PAGE, BLOG, SPECIAL OFFER, “and more.

CONCLUSION

Many websites are available in the market for creating a dynamic and responsive site, but every site is similar to each other, like Shopify, Magento, and WordPress, and this web application is like that, but with many new features that allow users to reach the site from bottom to top because in this web application, this paper uses new technologies like MongoDB, Express.js, React.js, Node.js, and Next.js, which can increase the number of web applications, among others. This application creates the website with full functionality, scalability, and custom power. The main powerful feature is that it is a user-friendly and user-recommended system. This application also provides such a level of security and cost-effectiveness that it will be available in a

multilingual, community-based, and performance-enhancing system. Many websites are available in the market for creating e-commerce sites, but no one is available in MERN stack technology, so it provides the main new feature and is fast for all of them. Many CMS web applications can't provide suggestion segmentation, but here this web application provides suggestion segmentation.

The future of content management systems for e-commerce holds exciting possibilities. As technology advances, this paper anticipates enhanced personalization features and streamlined integration with emerging online platforms. Also, another feature will be added in the future, which is product recommendation based on customer behavior using machine learning. The integration of blockchain for secure transactions and transparent supply chain management could become a standard, fostering trust among online shoppers.

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